

INTERLACE

Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

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Executive Summary

Stakeholder engagement is a central element of the INTERLACE project as it aims to co-produce tools, governance instruments and other project deliverables with local stakeholders, as well as facilitate knowledge exchange between local, regional and global stakeholders, to inform and support the restoration and rehabilitation of (peri)urban ecosystems through Nature-based Solutions. The purpose of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SES) is to give both theoretical and practical guidance to facilitate sustainable engagement of stakeholders in the INTERLACE project. In the first place, this guidance is meant for all INTERLACE partners who are involved with stakeholder engagement. Secondly, this guidance can be used by anyone who is involved with stakeholder engagement in urban Nature-based Solutions projects.

This guidance integrates an agile workflow and contains a logical step-to-step approach to create a tailored plan for engagement activities (see the 10 steps below, or download the visual summary [here](#)). To support this, an INTERLACE specific categorization of stakeholders is applied. Additionally, good practices are discussed and a troubleshooting section is included to support with possible challenges that can be encountered during stakeholder engagement.

Please use the Reading Guide on page 6 to jump straight to the sections of your interest.

Reading Guide

The '[Guidance document about the INTERLACE agile workflow implementation](#)' and the '[Guidance on gender, cultural and ethical consideration](#)' and the INTERLACE Stakeholder Engagement Strategy are closely related to – and depend on – each other. We recommend to read all three documents to fully grasp INTERLACE's ambitions to develop impactful products in corporation with stakeholders.

Use the table below to jump straight to the chapter that is of most interest to you. Want to start immediately with your stakeholder engagement? Then jump to chapter 3. Confused about all the terms and abbreviations? Then jump to the [glossary in Annex 1](#).

TITLE / CONTENT		TO LEARN MORE ABOUT...
1.	Introduction	The definition of stakeholder engagement and why it is central to the INTERLACE project.
1.1	Objective and goals	The purpose of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and who it is for.
1.2	Principles	The main principles at the basis of this strategy: participatory processes, inclusivity, impact and sustainable engagement.
1.3	INTERLACE context - setting the scene	INTERLACE cities, products and activities, and the agile workflow implemented in the project.
1.4	INTERLACE engagement mechanisms and platforms	The Impact Task Force, Local City Network Accelerators, Cities Talk Nature, City Focal Points, INTERLACE website, Innovation Hub and Product Lab.
2.	Stakeholder mapping	The logical categorization of stakeholders: a theoretical exercise to investigate how stakeholders will be engaged in the project.
2.1	Stakeholder roles	The 5 key stakeholder roles in the INTERLACE project: developers, shapers, end-users, enablers, interested public.
2.2	Stakeholder groups	The stakeholder groups defined from the stakeholder databases.
3.	Stakeholder Engagement Roadmap	A step-to-step approach to guide you in creating and conducting a tailor-made engagement strategy for your product or activity.
3.1	Plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why? - Set engagement objectives; 2. Who? - Identify stakeholders; 3. How? - Choose an appropriate format; 4. When? - Develop an implementation plan.
3.2	Engage	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Script - Practical and logistical organization of your engagement activity; 6. Invitation - Contact and invite stakeholders; 7. Roles - Transparent and clear engagement; 8. Follow-up.
3.3	Review	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Feedback; 10. Reflect & Improve.
4.	Good practices	The good practices to take into account when planning and conducting your tailored engagement activities.
5.	Troubleshooting	Risks and challenges to be aware of during stakeholder engagement processes, with proposed solutions or recommendations.

1. Introduction

Stakeholder engagement is a central element of the INTERLACE project. INTERLACE aims to co-produce tools, governance instruments and other project deliverables as well as exchange knowledge to inform and support the restoration and rehabilitation of (peri)urban ecosystems through Nature-based Solutions (NbS). Available knowledge and experiences on restorative NbS will be collected and incorporated within INTERLACE tools and instruments as well as shared through local, regional and global networks. Stakeholder engagement utilizes an inclusive, participatory approach to enable INTERLACE and wider stakeholders to collaboratively address urban challenges and develop solutions.

More concretely, within INTERLACE (and the six participating cities), stakeholders will be asked to share knowledge, expertise and perspectives as input for the development of INTERLACE products tailored to the (local) context, as well as exchange between INTERLACE cities and beyond to learn, share experiences and network. Furthermore, stakeholders are asked to test, validate, or to review INTERLACE products to increase applicability and usability.

As stakeholder input is crucial for the development of INTERLACE products, stakeholders should be engaged as early as possible in the project activities to optimize collaboration. INTERLACE aims to keep stakeholders engaged throughout the different phases of the project and therefore focuses on a sustainable engagement.

Stakeholder engagement can be described as a broad, inclusive and continuous process and an open, constructive relationship between a project and those potentially affected by or interested in it for a purpose to achieve accepted outcomes (Durham et al. 2014; AccountAbility, 2015). **Sustainable engagement** of stakeholders' places emphasis on engaging stakeholders in a long-term and meaningful way, or in other words, sustaining relationships and commitments between INTERLACE partners and its stakeholders (Israel et al. 2006).

Within the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SES), '**stakeholders**' are defined in a broad manner to ensure that a wide spectrum of stakeholders is considered for engagement. A stakeholder is defined as any group or individual who is potentially, directly or indirectly, interested in, affected by, or have an influence or impact on the project, its outputs or activities (Reed, 2008). This can include stakeholders that are close to the project and provide it with essential resources (knowledge, expertise, etc.), stakeholders that are impacted by or have influence over the city challenges or interventions planned to address the challenges. It can also include stakeholders who are more distant to the project but active or interested in restorative NbS (Sloan, 2009).

Stakeholder engagement is about building relationships with stakeholders and hence improving their trust, acceptance and willingness to participate, invest time and commitment and connect with other stakeholders that can support the project. Through the involvement of stakeholders, issues, concerns, expectations, interests and opportunities can be explored from various viewpoints, and a wide range of perspectives and knowledge can be gathered. By incorporating a greater quantity and diversity of knowledge and perspectives, INTERLACE is driven to create tailored, sustainable and more equitable products and activities adapted to local circumstances. Stakeholder engagement contributes to strengthening the credibility, uptake, replicability and upscalability of INTERLACE products.

1.1 Objective and goals

The purpose of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy is to give both theoretical and practical guidance to facilitate sustainable engagement of stakeholders in the INTERLACE project. This guidance is meant to support all INTERLACE partners who are involved with stakeholder engagement, from deliverable leads who engage stakeholders for input during product development to platform managers¹ who manage stakeholder interactions. The main ideas of the SES can also be used by anyone involved in stakeholder engagement for urban NbS projects.

The aim is to provide a logical and stepwise approach to stakeholder engagement for the different engagement purposes while considering the relevant stakeholder groups of the project. This strategy provides a baseline understanding and approach as a common and shared vision across INTERLACE that will need to be further adapted by each practitioner for tailored engagement activities. The strategy provides guidance for designing tailored approaches based on stakeholder roles within the project and stakeholder groups. The strategy aims to set out an easy-to-use Engagement Roadmap with pathways for engagement that is experienced as smooth and clear by the stakeholders, in which win-win conditions are identified for all parties. Furthermore, the strategy aims to provide guidance on involving all relevant stakeholder groups, including underrepresented groups. Where possible, the strategy includes practical INTERLACE examples of how the strategy can be applied. Annex 3 (Building the strategy) explains the used approach for the development of the strategy.

1.2 Engagement principles

The following principles are at the basis of the INTERLACE stakeholder engagement strategy:

- **Participatory processes** (based on Luyet et al., 2012);
 - Fair, equal, non-tokenistic² and transparent process that promotes equity, learning, trust, respect;
 - Integration of local, community-held and scientific knowledge;
 - Inclusion of stakeholders as active participants at an early stage;
 - Co-production and community co-ownership as principles;
 - Consideration for the historical social and ecological context where the product will be deployed/produced.
- **Inclusivity:** involve a representative group of stakeholders, paying particular attention to disadvantaged groups according to context, whether by gender, culture, age, class, sexual orientation, education, religion or ethnicity (as well as the intersections between these);

¹ Those who are responsible for one of the INTERLACE engagement mechanisms and platforms (see table 2 and 3 in section 1.4).

² “Tokenistic refers to actions that are the result of pretending to give advantage to those groups in society who are often treated unfairly, in order to give the appearance of fairness” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2021).

- **Impact:** generate impact by ensuring applicability, replicability and sustainability through participatory processes in which INTERLACE products are co-produced and reviewed by stakeholders to make sure the products meet their needs and expectations;
- **Sustainable engagement:** keep stakeholders interested, motivated and/or committed to participate throughout the products' lifespan within and beyond the project (from development to applying the product; for example, keeping stakeholders engaged through the lifespan of the City Network Accelerators (CNA)).

To read more about **participatory processes** and **inclusivity**, we refer to the Guidance on gender, cultural, and ethics-related considerations. This document provides tailored guidance for both the EU and CELAC regions to facilitate inclusive approaches. A set of easily applicable and measurable indicators to assess and monitor the cultural, gender and ethical concerns is also provided. This guidance was developed to ensure an inclusive participatory process for urban ecosystem restoration, and contributes to the stakeholder engagement strategy.

To read more about INTERLACE's approach about generating **impact** through co-production, we refer to the Agile Guidance and the Impact Task Force Report.

1.3 INTERLACE context – Setting the scene

INTERLACE brings together a unique international consortium with project partners spread across multiple organizations and cities. Central to the process are six committed EU and CELAC partner cities: Chemnitz (DE), Portoviejo (EC), Granollers (ES), Envigado (COL), Metropolia Krakowska (PL) and CBIMA-San José (CR) who have the ambition to restore and rehabilitate (peri-)urban ecosystems. All involved stakeholders of these cities collaborate in a participatory way, by co-producing instruments and tools (*products*) or taking part in knowledge exchange and outreach (*activities*) (see table 1 for some examples). **Henceforth, in this document 'activities' fall under the common denominator of 'products'**. In some instances, activities are still highlighted separately from products to emphasize the difference between the two.

Table 1. Examples of INTERLACE products and activities.

Products	Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban NbS Governance Atlas: interactive online database with good practice examples of policy and governance instruments for restorative urban NbS; • Tailor-made NbS assessment systems for each case study city; • Barometer to measure CNA engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events and activities organised by 'Cities Talk Nature' (regional and global CNAs); • Activities under the city engagement programme: design and implementation of the community arts programme, outdoor activities programme, digital gaming programme.

To establish and maintain the functional foundations for inclusive stakeholder engagement and collaboration across the project, INTERLACE is implementing an **agile workflow**. An iterative way of working in short cycles allows for early feedback and reflection moments during product development (see figure 1). A minimum of three development stages is recommended (product description, one intermediary stage and a final product).

This agile approach seeks to ensure the relevance, legitimacy and impact of project outputs, by presenting early product versions to stakeholders for their feedback. The goal is to ensure that the project products being developed for governments, decision-makers, urban planners, businesses, civil society groups, education initiatives or city networks meet these stakeholders' needs. Please refer to the Agile Guidance for more information.

Figure 1. Product development workflow in INTERLACE - an iterative way of working in short cycles allows for early feedback and reflection moments.

1.4 INTERLACE engagement mechanisms and platforms

Cooperation and participatory engagement is central to the INTERLACE project. To facilitate and strengthen these processes, several mechanisms and online platforms have been put into place. Table 2 gives an overview of the main engagement mechanisms in the project. Table 3 provides a list of the online platforms applied within the INTERLACE project to engage with stakeholders.

Table 2. Main mechanisms for engagement.

Engagement Mechanism	What?	Who? Target groups	Why? Objectives
<p>“Impact Task Force” (ITF)</p>	<p>Pool of stakeholders who play an active role in the project, by reviewing products and providing input and feedback from the end-user perspective.</p>	<p>The ITF is a pool of end-users which is continuously updated. This allows for stakeholders to join the ITF at any time. For each product a tailored ITF is set up.</p>	<p>To make sure the products meet the needs / expectations of stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • generating impact; • ensuring applicability; • ensuring replicability.
<p>Local City Network Accelerators</p>	<p>A central city exchange mechanism at local level to connect INTERLACE cities with their stakeholders.</p>	<p>A representative group of local stakeholders in each city, representing stakeholders most impacted by and/or having most influence on the challenges in each city and interventions undertaken³ in each city.</p>	<p>Create and promote:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exchange; • dialogue; • learning; • cooperation; • synergies, <p>between municipalities and other local stakeholders about urban ecosystem restoration and nature-based restorative solutions.</p>
<p>“Cities Talk Nature”</p> <p>Regional and Global City Network Accelerators</p> <p>More info in this YouTube video</p>	<p>A central city exchange mechanism and city-to-city pairings at regional and global level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Regional CNA's</u>: connect cities and their surrounding areas with other municipalities within the CELAC and EU regions; • <u>Global CNA</u>: foster an international city knowledge exchange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipalities and local governments (INTERLACE cities and beyond); • stakeholders in other projects; • city networks; • initiatives at local, regional and global level. 	<p>Create and promote:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exchange; • dialogue; • learning; • cooperation; • synergies, <p>between municipalities and other regional and global stakeholders about urban ecosystem restoration and nature-based restorative solutions.</p> <p>Multidirectional exchange of knowledge, experiences, initiatives and lessons learned.</p>
<p>City Focal Points (CFP)</p>	<p>CFPs are local city partners and local knowledge brokers (local research partners).</p>	<p>Each of the six INTERLACE City Focal Points consist of 1 or more city officials and 1 knowledge broker.</p>	<p>The CFPs oversee and shape engagement and co-production activities in each city.</p>

³ Interventions are not implemented by the project itself. Rather INTERLACE products in each city are supporting the design, implementation and monitoring of various interventions cities plan to undertake.

Table 3. Main online platforms within the INTERLACE project.

Platform	What?	Who? Target groups	Why? Objectives	How to use/join
 INTERLACE Project website	Project website	All project partners and stakeholders, with a focus on a wider interested public.	Interested public can: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • learn more about the project approach; • meet the team; • explore the INTERLACE cities; • receive project news. 	Visit the website: https://interlace-project.eu/
 INTERLACE Innovation Hub	An online community for sharing knowledge, ideas and stories about restoring nature in cities. Linked to Oppla (https://oppla.eu/), the EU Repository of Nature-based Solutions.	All project partners and stakeholders	Central repository of project resources and outcomes. Web-based platform for supporting stakeholder engagement and co-development processes.	Visit the website: https://interlace-hub.com/ Become a member by registering. This allows you to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute case studies, tools and articles relating to your own work; • participate in the City Groups; • early access to new features / product developments.
 Co-Production Platform = Product Lab	Online platform where the tools and resources created by the project will be made available for testing and feedback (integrated in the Hub)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All stakeholders co-creating products; • All members of the Impact Task Force. 	Tools for agile workflow, knowledge exchange and stakeholder dialogue / feedback.	Register to the Innovation Hub to get access to the Product Lab.
City microsites	Dedicated local language microsites for each INTERLACE city (integrated in the Hub)	Interested public (stakeholders at national and local city level)	Project awareness and facilitation of local activities	Register to the Innovation Hub to add/update content of the city microsites.

2. Stakeholder mapping

A **stakeholder mapping** exercise was conducted to identify, map and structure the stakeholder roles and their specific interests, impact, benefits and knowledge in such a way that each stakeholder will be engaged differently. The purpose of this stakeholder mapping was to make a logical categorization of stakeholders which require adapted approaches to engagement within INTERLACE. This was mainly a theoretical exercise to investigate how different stakeholders will be engaged in the project and to make a motivated and logical categorization.

The stakeholder mapping is considered the backbone of the SES on which further development of the strategy was based. Additionally, the results of the stakeholder mapping are used by the Communication Strategy (WP5). The results of this intermediate step was reviewed by a large part of the consortium (task leads, WP leads, knowledge brokers and the advisory board) as the SES concerns many INTERLACE tasks and activities, in order to avoid time-costly re-adjustments later on and to increase applicability of the strategy.

The stakeholder mapping builds on:

- Reviews of:
 - The INTERLACE project proposal: what ambitions does the project have for engaging stakeholders?
 - The various platforms within INTERLACE in which stakeholders are engaged: City Network Accelerator (local, regional, global), Impact Task Force, City Focal Points,

INTERLACE Hub. What are the goals of these platforms?

- The INTERLACE cities' stakeholder database (for the methodology see the Bibliography): what type of stakeholders have been identified in the different cities of the INTERLACE project?
- A questionnaire sent out to deliverable leads to ask which stakeholders are engaged in product development and who the envisioned end-users are;
- Several internal discussion rounds.

Based on the stakeholder mapping exercise, stakeholders can be categorized in **two different ways**:

- 1) **Stakeholder roles**: stakeholders are grouped based on their **role or function** within the INTERLACE project (see section 2.1);
- 2) **Stakeholder groups**: stakeholders are grouped based on their profession, knowledge, expertise or background, and are also grouped based on matching needs or interests (see section 2.2).

The difference between these two categories is that a stakeholder belongs to one stakeholder *group*, but can have multiple *roles* within the project. Taking into account these two aspects, will help improve the targeting and overall effectiveness of engagement and communication activities within INTERLACE. It enables tailored engagement and communication with stakeholders, based on:

- 1) their role within INTERLACE; and
- 2) taking into account challenges and good practices for engaging or communicating with a specific stakeholder group: the messages and methods they are most likely to respond to.

2.1 Stakeholder roles

In the INTERLACE project, **five key stakeholder roles** are considered in relation to INTERLACE products and activities (see figure 2 and table 4). A single stakeholder can take up one or more of these roles (changing over the course of the product development, or simultaneously during the product development) (figure 3).

Figure 2. Main stakeholder roles in relation to INTERLACE products and activities.

Figure 3. Stakeholder roles - each stakeholder can have multiple, overlapping roles.

Each of these stakeholder roles are connected to specific ‘calls to action’ (e.g. to decide, to develop), based on their role at a specific moment in time (table 4). Specific project examples are given below.

Table 4. Stakeholder roles within the INTERLACE project.

	Role	Calls to action	Interest	Influence
	Developers: stakeholders who are part of the development team, developing project products and activities (usually project partners).	<i>To develop, to organize, to lead, to engage.</i>	Invest knowledge / expertise for research and real-world applications.	Determines the vision and application of INTERLACE products.
	Shapers: stakeholders who provide input and feedback on project outputs.	<i>To review, to consult, to advice, to co-create, to test.</i>	Share (local) knowledge / expertise for tailor-made products and activities (increase usability and impact).	Can steer the design of elements within INTERLACE products.
	End-users: stakeholders who use the outputs of the INTERLACE project (products) for real-world applications outside the project.	<i>To use, to implement, to apply, to decide, to learn, to exchange knowledge, to participate, to partner up.</i>	Use of products or participation in activities that support the realization and knowledge exchange of NbS.	Real world application of INTERLACE products.
	Enablers: stakeholders who are capable of helping the project to reach and engage a diversity of other audiences, or to achieve other desirable impacts (e.g. promoting and disseminating project outputs). Have significant social capital and standing in a community.	<i>To enable, to provide access, to give mandate, to connect, to mediate, to disseminate, to promote.</i>	Provide the enabling environment for product development or the organization of activities.	Allows hard to reach communities to take up a role (developer, shaper end-user, enabler, public) within the project. Can provide access to, and incite communication and collaboration, with (local) hard to reach groups such as youth, elders, migrants, women, etc.
	Interested public: stakeholders who can generate ‘bottom-up’ support for NbS, and help translate the work of INTERLACE to other stakeholders (improved understanding, increased relevance).	<i>To learn, to be informed, to raise awareness, to have access to.</i>	Learning about NbS in general or specifically about INTERLACE activities, products and results.	Awareness raising (e.g. by sharing INTERLACE tools/stories).

Project examples:

- Urban NbS Governance Atlas - product

Project partners (*developers*) developed the Atlas according to the agile principles (see the Agile Guidance). An urban planning officer wants to use the final version of the online Atlas (*end-user*), but might also have provided feedback or entries to the Atlas (*shaper*).

- Cities Talk Nature (regional/global City Network Accelerators) - activities

Project partners (*developers*) developed the concept “Cities Talk Nature” (product). Through this product, engagement activities (events, webinars, letters) are organized for participants (*end-users*). Organizations which support “Cities Talk Nature” through dialogue (e.g. giving a slot at an event / webinar) and promotion of the activities, are *enablers*. Stakeholders who provided input / feedback during the development of the concept “Cities Talk Nature” are *shapers*.

- Agile Guidance - product

A small project development team developed guidelines for the INTERLACE agile workflow. During the process a larger group of project partners (*shapers*) were involved to help shape the first version. This first version is used by the entire consortium as *end-users* of the product. Once the INTERLACE project is completed, a wider audience might be interested in the lessons learned from this agile workflow (*interested public*). Therefore a public version is available, containing insights in applying an agile approach in an EU Horizon research and implementation project.

- Tailor-made NbS assessment framework for case study city - product

To adapt the pilot assessment framework to cities’ needs, cities are involved as *shapers* to make sure the end-results meet their expectations as an *end-user*. Also (academic) partners are consulted to identify a comprehensive list of tools that can be included in the assessment framework (*shapers*).

- Engagement programme at city scale - activities

An engagement programme is developed and implemented in the six INTERLACE partner cities. When developing the community arts programme, outdoor activities or digital gaming, the project team engages the City Focal Points who act as *shapers* (help to design the specific programme and activities to the local context). The CFP’s can also act as *enablers* (e.g., contact a community leader to mobilize a neighbourhood in the city to take part in these INTERLACE activities). The participants are considered the *end-users* of the activities. The *interested public* may be people who want to read up and learn about the event and outcomes (through e.g. a blog post on the website), after the event has taken place.

The described stakeholder roles (table 4) can be applied to internal project partners and external stakeholders of the project. No distinction will be made between ‘internal’ and ‘external’ stakeholders throughout the SES, except for the following instance. The role of developer is considered to be a role that will mainly be taken up by internal project partners. **The SES will not focus further on the engagement of developers and refers to the Agile Guidance for guidance on identifying and collaborating with the product developers.** There may be a rare occasion (due to the time and commitment needed) where an external stakeholder will play the role of developer, by joining the product development team. This is also covered in the Agile workflow. Furthermore, it is the role of the developer (deliverable/task lead) to apply the SES to engage with the other roles.

2.2 Stakeholder groups

To map these stakeholder groups as close as possible to the reality of the INTERLACE cities and activities, the categories are defined with input from the stakeholder databases and from a questionnaire shared with project deliverable leads. The categorization of stakeholder groups (table 5) uses a 'flat' hierarchy and does not list these groups in order of importance.

Table 5. Stakeholder groups within the INTERLACE project.

Stakeholder groups	Sub-groups
<p>Political representatives: those who are elected in public office and make political decisions within governmental settings.</p> <p><i>For example: mayors, city council members, ministers, elected officials, political leaders.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National ● Regional ● Local
<p>Governmental authorities: those who develop laws, strategies or plans and administrators who are controlling and maintaining these laws.</p> <p><i>For example: policy makers, urban planners, public administration, public servants, municipal departments.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National ● Regional ● Local
<p>Civil society: those who hold the space for collective action around shared interests, purposes and values, generally distinct from government and commercial for-profit stakeholders.</p> <p>The first group is highlighted as it needs to be an active part of any participatory process. Efforts on having them on board are worth making, and this is not always easy.</p> <p><i>For example: see sub-groups.</i></p>	<p>Groups that consist mainly out of citizens / more informal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community groups ● Neighbourhood associations ● Indigenous groups ● Women organizations ● Youth groups ● Representatives from informal settlements
	<p>Groups that have employees / more formal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NGO's ● Environmental and social movements ● Trade unions (env. sector) ● Charitable organizations ● Faith-based organizations ● Professional associations ● Cultural institutes
<p>Academia, research and education: those doing research and wanting to advance knowledge and/or share knowledge to students and interested parties.</p> <p><i>For example: research institutes, universities, (high or primary) schools, training centres, environmental education projects.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific institutes ● Education institutes <p>According to context, particularly important for Latin America:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Traditional Ecological Knowledge holders ● Indigenous Knowledge holders
<p>Private sector: those who make part of a country's economic system and run individual and company businesses with the intention to make</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Private companies

Stakeholder groups	Sub-groups
<p>profit.</p> <p><i>For example: local industry, companies, consultancies, design agency, architecture offices, SMEs, co-operatives, landowners, land managers, farmers.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Landowners and managers ● Nature-based Enterprises (NBEs)
<p>Media: those who produce and spread news and stories.</p> <p><i>For example: (local) newspapers, magazines, radio, television, social media.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● News media companies ● Leaders of opinion ● Influencers
<p>Networks: where a mix of audiences connect/meet.</p> <p><i>For example: 'Cities Talk Nature', national associations of municipalities/local governments.</i></p>	
<p>Finance sector and funders: those who have access to financial resources and want to invest in promoting NbS / achieving sustainability goals.</p> <p><i>For example: banks, foundations, corporations.</i></p>	

Another element to consider when engaging and communicating with stakeholders is their (work) field. Communication can be adapted and targeted to a specific field to spark their interest in engagement in the project. (Work) fields cross stakeholder groups. For example, the nature field can consist of public entities, private organizations, civil organizations, research institutes, etc. Fields that can be considered to be included in INTERLACE are, among others: nature, environment (e.g., climate), water, agriculture, recreation, social, culture.

3. Engagement Roadmap

The stakeholder Engagement Roadmap is a logical step-to-step guide to create and conduct a tailor-made engagement strategy. The roadmap is based on the engagement principles (section 1.2), good practices (chapter 4) and troubleshooting (chapter 5) as well as the outcomes of the stakeholder mapping (chapter 2). Figure 4 presents the 3 phases and 10 steps of the roadmap. The first phase focuses on planning the engagement activities (section 3.1), the second phase focuses on steps to take during each engagement activity (section 3.2) and phase 3 focuses on reviewing each engagement activity (section 3.3). The circle represents the iterative characteristic of the Engagement Roadmap. When working with stakeholders and participatory processes, unpredictability is inevitable (e.g., responses or reactions from participants during the engagement activity or changes in the political agenda). An iterative and flexible approach enables you to adapt to these new and unforeseen circumstances (Gray 2008, Agile Guidance). Annex 2 presents an example of the application of the Engagement Roadmap.

Figure 4. Overview of the INTERLACE Engagement Roadmap.

When planning for stakeholder engagement, we recommend to take into account the **agile workflow** of the product development (consult the Agile Guidance for more details). A validated and clear product vision is recommended to communicate with those involved. A clear **vision** and **purpose** of your product helps with your own understanding, as well as for all others involved.

Ideally, stakeholders are directly involved when defining the vision and purpose of the product. This allows for meaningful participation. If possible, the vision is developed through research on the social context, including socio-ecological needs and expectations of stakeholders.

When it is impossible to involve the stakeholders from the beginning, start by explaining your vision and purpose of your product to the stakeholders and collect their views and opinions. Depending on the degree of stakeholder involvement, the product vision might change, based on their feedback. This is also an opportunity to talk about product requirements, in the form of “user stories”: through dialogue

you map out who the stakeholders are, what they expect from the product and why (more on user stories in the Agile Guidance).

Applying step 1, 2 and 3 for validating your product vision

Collecting feedback from stakeholders on your product vision can be considered your first engagement activity. As this step is very similar for all products, we apply (as far as possible) steps 1 (engagement objective), 2 (who to engage) and 3 (format) to guide the first engagement activity:

Objective: “The stakeholder(s) review the product vision in order to have a shared understanding and express expectations or user requirements”.

Who to engage: stakeholders who will apply, use, participate in (e.g., in case of a network event) your product.

Format: Either a physical meeting or online. The agile team prepared a template Miro board that can be used for online workshops to collect feedback on the product vision and create user stories (see Annex 4 for an example).

3.1 Plan

Step 1. Why? - Set engagement objectives

Start planning your engagement activities as soon as possible - e.g when your product vision is validated - in order to be able to engage stakeholders through different phases of your product development. Before deciding which stakeholders to engage and through what format, it is important to get your purpose and objectives clear for yourself but also to communicate to the stakeholders during (the preparations of) the engagement (steps 6 and 7). The purpose of your engagement can be described in terms of success: what would be gained from successful engagement?

Define what success looks like

Describe what successful engagement looks like to you. This can require some thought. For example, does success count as numbers of stakeholders engaged (e.g., for a public event), or is it considered successful when a co-production process resulted in creative or innovative ideas, or when the stakeholders' awareness is raised or their behaviour is changed? Having defined what success looks like, will further support your planning phase (which stakeholders and formats are suited to reach success?) and will also help with your reflection afterwards (step 10).

The purpose of your engagement can be refined into multiple (more specific) engagement objectives. Our template for an engagement objective includes a '**stakeholder role**', '**call to action**' and the **added value**.

Define stakeholder engagement objective

"For my product, the -- stakeholder role -- will -- call to action -- in order to -- added value(s) of engagement --".

Stakeholders can be engaged for different actions during different phases of the product development. We have called this 'call to action'. Each objective has one call to action. The calls to action are linked to the stakeholder roles. In table 6 you can find the calls to action that are most likely to be applied within INTERLACE, but you may link other similar calls to action to these stakeholders roles. For defining your stakeholder engagement objectives, think of calls to action needed over the course of your product development, but also about calls to action when your product is finalized.

Once the calls to actions are selected, they can be combined with the envisioned **added values** for your product. At a later stage, when it is clear which stakeholder groups are to be engaged, also the **benefits** for these stakeholders will be defined (win-wins). Table 8 presents a list of added values per stakeholder role. This table can be used as a basis or as inspiration for defining the added value of your engagement plans.

INTERLACE examples of engagement objectives:

- For the Urban NbS Governance Atlas:
 - The shapers will test the prototype of the online interface, in order to get feedback on user-friendliness and extra requirements;
 - The end-users will use the Atlas, in order to learn about different governance approaches for Urban NbS.
- For 'Cities Talk Nature'-webinars:
 - Shapers will review the Cities Talk Nature approach in order to increase relevance for the participants and quality assurance;
 - End-users will exchange knowledge about restorative NbS and INTERLACE products, in order to learn from each other's experiences.

- For the Community Arts Programme:
 - Enablers will connect product developers with local artists in order to let them participate in the event;
 - Local shapers will advise the product developers on the city event in order to get a clear picture of what is feasible and desirable;
 - The art groups across participating cities (shapers) will co-create public artworks in order to interact with each other, sharing their stories and sources of inspiration;
 - Interested public will be informed about urban NbS through the public artworks in order to create awareness and public support for future NbS activities.

Applying the calls to action to the different stakeholder roles

At the end of each product development, there will always be **end-users**. The call to action can be defined based on the product vision: e.g., is the product used or applied for NbS decision-making, or implementation, or is it rather about sharing knowledge through events?

There will also be **shapers** during most, if not all, product development cycles. The calls to action contain different forms of stakeholder involvement during product development. The Agile Guidance suggests co-production with regular reviews of intermediate products. This can be done in various ways. Participation can be seen as a continuum with on one side minimum involvement of stakeholders such as information sessions and on the other side high levels of participation through which stakeholders take part as co-creators (Edelenbos, 2000; REVIT, 2007; IAP2, 2018). Following a simplified version of the participation spectrum we distinguish a light, medium and high degree of engagement, depending on the call to action (table 7). A higher degree of engagement means a more balanced power distribution between developers and stakeholders. Deciding on the degree of engagement depends on, among others, the purpose of the product, end-users, ambition and available resources (time and budget).

Whether you need **enablers** can be decided during this step, but also at a later stage when it is clear which stakeholders you aim to engage. It is possible that you realize at that point you need enablers to reach certain stakeholder groups.

When you want to inform or raise awareness about your products, or make your product available beyond the envisioned end-users, the **interested public** comes into play. Focus on sub-groups of the public on which the project can have an impact.

ACTION 1: Define your engagement **objectives** for your product development in terms of ‘calls to action’ and added value. Specify which **role** is needed during what phase of your product development.

Table 6. Call to action linked to stakeholders roles.

Role	Call to action	Explanation
Shaper	to consult / review	Stakeholders provide feedback on an intermediate/draft version of a product.
	to advise	Stakeholders are involved early in the product development in which their ideas have a fully-fledged role in shaping the final product.
	to co-create	Stakeholders and developers agree together on the product vision and both play an equal role in developing the final product.
	to test	Stakeholders are asked to test a tool, instrument etc. for real-world applicability.
End-user	to use / implement / apply	Stakeholders want to implement NbS and use / apply INTERLACE products.
	to decide	Stakeholders want to decide on which NbS actions to take and apply INTERLACE's products.
	to learn / exchange knowledge	Stakeholders want to learn from experts, cities or other stakeholders about their experiences and expertise on urban NbS.
	to participate	Participation of stakeholders in INTERLACE activities (networks, engagement programmes,...).
	to partner up	Different stakeholders partner up through an INTERLACE mechanism (Cities Talk Nature).
Enabler	to enable / provide access	Stakeholders can enable conditions and provide access to hard-to-reach stakeholders.
	to give mandate	Stakeholders can give a mandate to conduct (research) activities or to apply products in a specific location / context.
	to mediate	Stakeholders can mediate between developers and stakeholders.
	to disseminate / promote	Stakeholders can disseminate / promote INTERLACE activities, products, reports, information, tools, etc. to their network.
Interested public	to learn	Stakeholders want to learn about NbS and INTERLACE products and activities.
	to be informed	Stakeholders want to stay informed about INTERLACE and its products and activities.
	to raise awareness	Stakeholders want to raise their awareness about NbS and INTERLACE products and activities.
	to have access to	Stakeholders want to have access to INTERLACE products.

Table 7. Degree of engagement. Based on Edelenbos, 2000.

Call to action	Degree of engagement	Timing during product development process	Power distribution
To consult / review	Light	Halfway to late	Developers ask stakeholders for feedback or input on intentions, plans or drafts. Developers decide whether to incorporate the received feedback or input.
To advise	Medium	Early	The developers set preconditions that the product should meet. Stakeholders can provide their ideas for the aims and content (problem definition, solutions, etc.) of the product and are involved during all stages of the development. The developers incorporate the stakeholder's input when it meets the preconditions or justify their decision to not incorporate it.
To co-create	High	Early	Developers and stakeholders are equals during the whole product development process. Developers and stakeholders decide together on aims and content of the product and the preconditions the product should meet.

Table 8. Added values of engaging stakeholder roles.

Role	Added values of engagement
Shapers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-scale and multi-sectoral input on the design and development of INTERLACE products; • Range of expertise, technical knowledge, local knowledge; • Product testing and quality assurance (increased user confidence); • Enhances stakeholder ownership of the products (in case the shaper is also the end-user); • Achieving mutually valued outcomes.
End-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of INTERLACE outputs for real-world applications (Impact!); • Crucial to ensure INTERLACE outputs are fit for purpose and achieve uptake amongst end users.
Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier access to target audiences; and increased number of stakeholders; • 'Amplification' of communication and dissemination activities; • Increased field of action for the project; • Implementation of various opportunities in local contexts; • Participation at different levels.
Interested public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create awareness, broader engagement, and public support; • 'Translate' the work of INTERLACE to the wider society (clearer, simpler, more understandable); • Evidence public support that can be used by city authorities to leverage ongoing/ legacy activities beyond the project.

Step 2. Who? - Identify stakeholders

- **Define which stakeholder groups to engage**

When the engagement objectives are clear, you can explore which **stakeholder groups** you want to involve for each objective. Once the stakeholder groups are known, specific stakeholders within that group can be searched for. Table 5 (stakeholder groups) presents the most relevant stakeholder groups for INTERLACE. When identifying these groups, the following questions can be asked:

- Which groups are likely to be **affected** directly (by the product) or indirectly (by the city challenge(s) or by the implementation of NbS)?
- Which groups are likely to be **interested** directly (in the product) or indirectly (in the city challenge(s) or in the implementation of NbS)?
- Which groups have **influence** or power over the city challenges or the implementation of NbS?

Furthermore, the selection of stakeholder groups can be motivated by what **added value** their engagement provides. Table 9 presents a list of added values per stakeholder group.

Table 9. Added values of engaging stakeholder groups relevant for INTERLACE.

GROUP	Added values of engagement
Political representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local political support/mandate for INTERLACE activities; • Access to decision makers and possibly their networks; • Development of NbS on (municipal) political agenda; • Knowledge/expertise on city challenges and their politics; • Decision making in favour of NbS; • Allocating resources for NbS.
Governmental authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge/expertise on city challenges and current policies, governance approaches, available tools and data; • Internal support within municipal departments for INTERLACE products; • INTERLACE products contributing to urban (NbS) planning and policy making.
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge on city challenges; • Include local and cultural knowledge and expertise in INTERLACE products or activities; • Sensitivity to local issues/needs/wishes; • Raising awareness and participation; • Volunteering/stewardship; • Citizen science (citizens collecting data / monitoring); • Public support; • Sense of place and local identity to project activities; • Opportunities for innovative press/media and communications; • Knowledge exchange; • Possible access to data owned by NGO's or collaboration on data collection;

GROUP	Added values of engagement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Possibility to make links with existing (restoration) projects which the NGO leads; ● Amplifying communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to reach new audiences and increase impact.
Academia, research and education sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● State of art of academic advancements around INTERLACE research topics; ● Researchers as knowledge brokers to bring ideas to the cities; ● Improved quality assurance of INTERLACE products (increased user confidence); ● Share knowledge to students / youth on importance of urban green or more specific INTERLACE results; ● Share knowledge to schools / teachers who can use it in their lessons; ● Have access /get input from a younger generation; ● Increase awareness and participation; ● Potential for increased innovation and experimentation.
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sectoral (technical) expertise and can support/contribute NbS design and implementation; ● Impact on privately owned land; ● Knowledge exchange between public sector and private sector; ● ‘Ground-truthing’ of products by private sector practitioners; ● Potential for exploitation of product results and increased impact; ● Improved quality assurance of INTERLACE products (increased user confidence).
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sharing work, results, impact with a wider audience; ● Promotion; ● Awareness raising & empowerment; ● ‘De-mystifying’ the science to help reach and engage the wider public; ● Engaging in debates on NbS interventions and addressing community / activist concerns; ● Targeted engagement of professional audiences through sector/industry-specific media.
(Inter)national organisations or networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sharing work, results, impact with a wider audience; ● Promotion; ● Awareness raising.
Finance sector and funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identification of financing opportunities for NbS; ● Helping to determine the financial viability / sustainability of INTERLACE products; ● Opportunity to facilitate significant impact - e.g., matching INTERLACE products with local practitioners/ businesses and funders as part of exploitation activities; ● Motivating and giving confidence to private sector involvement in INTERLACE.

- **Identify specific stakeholders**

When it is clear which stakeholder roles and groups are to be engaged, **specific stakeholders** can be identified. INTERLACE developed and applied the Methodology Living Stakeholder Database to create an overview of relevant stakeholders for each city. Here we also consider who is affected by or interested in the product and the benefit of engagement. Furthermore, the ITF or local enablers can be consulted to identify stakeholders. When possible, try to be as detailed as possible by not only identifying organizations, but also (when applicable) relevant departments of organizations and which individuals.

Taking into consideration the engagement principles (section 1.2), it is recommended to engage a high **diversity** of stakeholders, in order to have a wide diversity of perspectives, especially for the ‘shapers’ role. Therefore, we recommend to go beyond the usual suspects. You can further read on inclusivity considerations in the Guidance on gender, cultural, and ethics-related considerations. Furthermore, Annex 2 of the Methodology Living Stakeholder Database proposes some guiding questions to identify relevant stakeholders.

- **Consider if enablers are needed**

When you have identified the stakeholders, it is possible that challenges occur to actually engage them. Therefore, it is important to reflect and consider if you need certain **enablers** (intermediaries between you and the groups) to reach out to certain stakeholders. If so, go back to your engagement objectives and add a new objective specifically for this.

For example: ***“For my product, the enabler will mediate between the developers and -envisioned group- in order to obtain local knowledge relevant for the product development.”***

Try to identify who could have this enabler role, e.g. organisations working with a specific stakeholder group.

- **Determine engagement benefits**

When it is clear which stakeholders you aim to engage, it is time to identify the engagement benefits or why it would be interesting for them to engage with the product. Communicating tailored elements that may spark their interest increases the likelihood of the stakeholders answering the call to action (see also step 6).

Identifying **engagement benefits** for your stakeholders is based on the *role* they are asked to play and the stakeholder *group* they are part of. Table 10 presents a general list of benefits based on the stakeholder *roles* and table 11 presents a general list of benefits based on stakeholder *groups*. Tailored communication of benefits can be made by combining benefits from the stakeholder roles with benefits from the stakeholder groups. Additionally, **sectoral motivations** a stakeholder might have in relation to the project can be included to further tailor the communication. Consider motivations related to the environment, social cohesion, health, recreation, aesthetics, etc.

Table 10 Engagement benefits for stakeholder roles.

ROLE	Engagement benefits for stakeholder roles
Shapers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Steer content of products to meet (1) the state-of-the-art or (2) the context of the INTERLACE cities, and by doing so increase usefulness and relevance of the products; ● Opportunity to influence product development to ensure outputs are adequate to their needs; ● Opportunity to share knowledge and expertise in new and/or more impactful ways; ● Opportunity to bring existing ideas into reality with support of other stakeholders and INTERLACE funding.
End-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge based decision-making and planning of NbS through tailor made products; ● Knowledge exchange between cities, regions, academia and other experts; ● Better quality products that improve users' own workflow and outputs; ● Opportunity to draw upon high-level knowledge and expertise of project partners.
Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Being able to give unheard / hard to reach voices a platform or to spread knowledge to groups that may be interested but hard to reach; ● Helping their own users/ members/ beneficiaries benefit from being involved in INTERLACE; ● Access to an international platform for their own outreach and awareness raising related to NbS; ● Value of being associated with a high profile EU-funded project.
Interested public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improving skills, knowledge and capabilities of public groups working to improve nature in cities; ● Helping public groups bring about positive change / development that might not be possible in the absence of the project; ● Spread of information and knowledge of urban nature; ● Helping people gain new skills and knowledge useful for employment and personal development; ● Enabling new/stronger relationships with city authorities and other key stakeholders that might otherwise be 'out of reach' of public groups.

Table 11. Engagement benefits for stakeholder groups.

GROUP	Engagement benefits for stakeholder groups
Political representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evidence and tools to improve decision making for NbS; ● Innovative and green alternatives for city challenges; ● Innovative alternatives to mobilize resources for NbS; ● Realizing their political agenda; ● Learning and sharing knowledge with academia, experts, other cities and local stakeholders.
Governmental authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evidence and tools to improve implementation of NbS; ● Innovative alternatives / inspiration for urban green policies; ● Innovative alternatives / inspiration for urban green governance; ● Learning and sharing knowledge with academia, experts, other cities and local stakeholders.
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participation in INTERLACE activities which may influence urban design decisions; ● Opportunities for bottom-up initiatives; ● Learning opportunity about urban NbS; ● Possibilities to address their agenda in INTERLACE cities and have influence on the causes they stand for; ● INTERLACE can provide a stepping stone for future partnerships with the local government of each INTERLACE city; ● Knowledge exchange between city, academia and other experts; ● Increased sense of ownership; ● Raising own profile through association with an EU-funded project; ● Network opportunities.
Academia, research and education sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide input to INTERLACE products (being able to influence / steer end-products); ● Access to new knowledge and insights from INTERLACE scientific research; ● Access to case studies; ● Networking opportunities with knowledge exchange between academics, cities and other experts; ● Professional development and impact; ● Opportunity for youth / students to provide input on their cities green spaces; ● Opportunities to link to environmental education projects (or to set up such projects).
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having influence on INTERLACE tools / NbS implementation; ● Evidence and tools to improve implementation of NbS on privately owned land; ● INTERLACE can provide a stepping stone for public-private partnerships; ● Learn about NbS options for their own properties; ● Unique access to high-level knowledge and expertise from the scientific community (in Latin America and EU); ● Unique access to potential clients and partners within and beyond cities; ● Possibilities of new NbS projects to collaborate with the city for private organizations working in that field; ● Networking opportunities with knowledge exchange between academics, cities and local stakeholders;

GROUP	Engagement benefits for stakeholder groups
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Raising their own profile amongst the expert community and with potential partners and/or clients.
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interesting and positive local stories; ● New perspectives on the 'usual environmental story'; ● Human-interest stories (from working with local communities).
(Inter)national organisations or networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Learning opportunity about urban green / NbS; ● Knowledge exchange.
Finance sector and funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to state-of-the-art research and new products related to (peri-)urban development; ● Potential to identify 'fundable' new projects and opportunities; ● Identification of cities where their targets can be achieved (SDGs, GHG emissions, etc.).

Furthermore, in order to create additional impact, investigate whether your product and engagement activities can be linked to other ongoing processes, plans, activities or actions. This may identify synergies and can provide additional motivation for stakeholders to participate if these linkages are made explicit. For example, INTERLACE engagement activities provide input to the cities' NbS planning and implementation and will feed concrete actions. This will lift the engagement activities from being merely a contribution to a study, tool development or knowledge exchange, to something that has impact on the ground, which makes it more interesting for stakeholders.

Additional benefits to building relationships of trust

When you plan to engage the same group of stakeholders for a longer period, you can consider generating additional stakeholder benefits for them. For example, you can consider organizing activities that are not necessarily related to your product such as a webinar to learn about a topic, a reception, an excursion to learn about the area, issues, local products, etc. These extras may contribute to the motivation of stakeholders to stay engaged. Such informal exchanges can help to get to know each other better and support building a trust relationship.

Such activities can also be organized to enhance your connection with one or a few stakeholders to improve trust between both parties. E.g., having an informal activity with a group of vulnerable stakeholders can allow them to get to know you and understand your intentions, as well as you getting to know them and their needs, expectations, sensitivities, etc. (Rodriguez-Melo & Mansouri, 2011).

ACTION 2:

- Define which **stakeholder group(s)** you want to engage for each engagement objective, taking into account diversity and inclusiveness.
- Define **specific stakeholders** you want to engage. Write down the organizations and when applicable the departments and individuals.
- Reflect whether you can **reach** all the stakeholders you aim to engage, and whether **enablers** need to be identified.
- Identify **benefits** for the stakeholders related to their engagement, based on their role and the group they are part of. Additionally, **sectoral motivations** can be taken into account as well as **synergies** that go beyond the INTERLACE project.

Step 3. How? - Choose an appropriate format

To achieve a successful engagement outcome, it is important to select the appropriate formats for engagement. For each engagement objective, a fitting format needs to be selected. Table 12 presents various suggestions for engagement formats based on the stakeholder role. Choose the format or methods that will allow you to reach a successful outcome.

Table 12. Engagement formats and supporting mechanisms per role.

ROLE	Format	INTERLACE mechanisms
Shaper	Workshops, focus groups, interviews, questionnaires, e-mails	ITF, CNA
End-user	(Network) events, conferences, written media	ITF, CNA, Hub
Enabler	E-mails, (video-)calls, one-on-one meetings	CFP, Knowledge broker
Interested public	Written media (magazine, newspaper, report, etc.), social-media, video, posters, public events	Website, Hub

There are multiple considerations to take into account when deciding on the appropriate format, such as:

- Socio-cultural considerations:
 - Will the stakeholders feel comfortable/safe with the chosen format? Stakeholders can be approached separately or through different formats if there are any potential sensitivities, conflicts, strong power-relations or instances of discrimination. For example, when there are risks of conflict, or in case you want to engage with marginalised stakeholders, bilateral engagement may be better suited to ensure all voices are openly heard in a safe environment.
 - Consider how to overcome language barriers (translations and non-technical language).
- Organizational and logistical considerations:
 - Location: the choice of venue, outside location or online platform can have positive or negative potential effects on the engagement process and its outcomes, so give this appropriate consideration (Gray, 2008).
 - Timing: are there any other interventions, projects, programmes, campaigns ongoing or planned that could interfere or be linked?
 - Adjust the format to the time stakeholders have available.
 - Be mindful of different time zones.
- Resources - what is necessary so stakeholders can be engaged meaningfully:
 - Availability of time, staff, budget, equipment, capacity (skills/knowledge) - does this match with the goals and ambitions?
 - Do all stakeholders have resources to be able to participate? If not, are there ways to provide these resources? For example, a bus-ticket to the venue, access to phone, computer, stable internet, etc.
 - Are there other conditions stakeholders need/require before being able to participate?
- Health considerations, especially regarding Covid-19: is it possible to organize engagement activities (with restrictions) or should online alternatives be considered?

To get a good view on these considerations, organize a meeting with a partner that is close to the context in which you will engage stakeholders. For example, a city representative who can give you insights on local considerations to be taken into account.

Facilitation

In the INTERLACE project, usually someone from the development team will be responsible for delivering the engagement process. Decide on who will take on the role of facilitator during the engagement activity. In some cases, an external facilitator might be necessary (e.g., when an independent or a more locally tailored facilitation is required, to the local context or a specific stakeholder group). In any case, if an external facilitator is deemed necessary, this person should be involved as early as possible to better plan the processes and provide realistic guidance.

ACTION 3: Select an **appropriate format** for each engagement objective.

Step 4. When? - Implementation plan

All the decisions made and information collected in steps 1 to 3 are merged into an implementation plan. The implementation plan is a logical order of your planned engagement activities, their objectives, who to engage and through which format. In order to plan accordingly, it should be made clear in which order your engagement activities need to be done. One engagement activity might be dependable on another. For example, first an enabler needs to be engaged before a certain stakeholder can be involved in other engagement activities. Set out an overall timeline with an estimation of dates and be realistic about how long things take. Always allow more rather than less time for planning and for people to get involved (time is needed between events for work to be completed and to be taken to the next stage) (Gray, 2008).

This implementation plan is linked to the product development stages (or iterations) of the agile workflow (Agile Guidance). Each development stage (or iteration) delivers an intermediary version of the product, ready for users to test or review. This intermediary version should already hold a certain value to the stakeholders. When setting out the overall timeline for engagement, decide on the appropriate times to engage with the stakeholders about the intermediary versions (when will these versions be ready to share, how much time do they need to review or test?).

Figure 5 is an example of how such an implementation plan looks like. Your implementation plan should not be a copy of this example, in terms of the number of activities or stakeholders shown. This example is made to highlight the following elements:

- Each engagement activity has its own objective;
- For each engagement activity different stakeholders can be involved;
- Each engagement activity has its own format (nevertheless, a format can be used multiple times when appropriate);
- Ideally, engagement activity 1 is to create a product vision and will therefore always have a similar objective;

- It is possible that only one stakeholder is engaged during one engagement activity, e.g., engaging an enabler to be able to gain access to other stakeholders;
- Based on multiple considerations (step 3), one engagement activity can have different formats for different stakeholders;
- The same stakeholder can have different engagement benefits during different engagement activities;
- The number of engagement activities during product development and when a product is finalized depends on the product and the availability of stakeholders;
 - Cities Talk Nature as an example: the product vision of Cities Talk Nature is to set up a network through which regular engagement activities are organized and hosted. The product development is to set up this network and the final product is to apply the network to engage end-users. In comparison, there are more engagement activities with the finalized product (all Cities Talk Nature events), than during product development.
 - Governance Atlas as an example: the product vision of the Governance Atlas is to create an interactive online database with good practice examples of governance and policy instruments. During product development, multiple engagement activities can be organized to collect input on needs and wishes on the content and interface of the database, as well as test and review intermediate products. Once the product is finalized, engagement activities will shift towards dissemination activities.

We recommend letting your implementation plan to be reviewed before starting your engagement activities by project partners and stakeholders. The implementation plan can also be updated after each engagement activities when new insights occur during review (phase 3: review). E.g. when interacting with an enabler, it becomes clear you need a different format for an underrepresented stakeholder, or your list of stakeholders for a future engagement activity expands after you receive recommendations from stakeholders during an engagement activity.

ACTION 4: Create a (living) implementation plan which presents a logical order of your engagement activities as well as the when, why, who and how?

Figure 5. Structure implementation plan

3.2 Engage

This second phase is where the calls to action outlined in your implementation plan are put into practice. Where phase 1 provided steps for the overall planning of all your engagement activities, phase 2 provides steps that should be applied for **each individual** engagement activity. In this phase we mainly focus on a step-wise approach for communication with the stakeholders before, during and after engagement. For general good practices during engagement we refer to chapter 4.

Step 5. Script - Practical and logistical organization of your engagement activity

A script should be made for larger engagement activities to support its organization. A script template can be found in Annex 5 and contains elements such as what materials are needed, who will arrange what, and contains a script for the day itself (who presents at what time, who facilitates, etc.). Also include the methods you will apply in the script. Specifically for virtual engagement activities, you can consult the Cookbook Virtual Exchange Formats for a collection of innovative, inclusive and interactive exchange methods and tools to facilitate city-to-city exchange.

In some cases, especially when organizing a larger engagement event (e.g. a webinar as part of Cities Talk Nature, or a digital gaming programme for youth in their neighbourhood), consider collecting input from the stakeholders prior to the event. Stakeholders can provide feedback on your engagement activity in order to align your plans with their expectations.

Examples:

- Cities Talk Nature webinar: prior to the event, organize a survey to ask the audience which subjects they prefer to see on the webinar agenda (e.g. voting on proposed subjects and possibility to add new items).
- Digital gaming programme: present the draft ideas or gaming prototypes to young people and children, before the actual event. This might generate some interesting insights to help fine tune for optimal results.

ACTION 5: Make a detailed script to support the organization of your engagement activity.

Share your plans with the stakeholders and collect feedback to increase relevance and impact of your activity.

Step 6. Invitation - Contact and invite stakeholders

When inviting stakeholders for your engagement activity, try to contact individuals (when identified in step 2) rather than organisations. It is more likely to receive a response from individuals. However, give them the opportunity to nominate better suited colleagues.

During the first contact with stakeholders, it is important to send out tailored communication depending on the stakeholder (group) and the call to action (role). The messages to stakeholders should be tailored to suit their situation and mindset instead of just "telling" them something general about your product. For example, stakeholders with low awareness about an activity may need more background information; stakeholders not being very supportive of the product or activity may need messages that highlight benefits to them specifically. The following should be communicated clearly (based on AccountAbility, 2015):

- Introduction to the project and your product (product vision);
- The goals of the engagement (call to action + added value);
- What is expected from them (including time investment);
- The benefits to the stakeholder (benefits role + group);
- The planned engagement process (format + timeline);
- Logistical and practical information about the engagement;
- How to respond to the invitation.

Stakeholders can be contacted through different means, such as e-mails, phone calls, social media, etc. Stakeholders may have different preferences on how they are contacted. If you want to contact multiple individuals (e.g. shapers), e-mail or phone-calls are better suited. If you want to reach out to a wide group of people (e.g. interested public), other means are better suited, such as social media, or other physical or virtual outlets. In case you need an enabler to reach out to a certain group, let the enabler make the first contact and agree who (you or the enabler) as well as how you will communicate during the course of the project with the respective stakeholders.

When necessary, brief the stakeholders who responded to your invitation. It might be possible that you want the stakeholders to be prepared when they participate in your engagement activity. Disseminate relevant information in advance and present the content in a readily understandable format and language to ensure it is meaningful for the stakeholders. Give stakeholders sufficient preparation time and briefing to form well-informed opinions and decisions.

Keep track of which stakeholders you contact, through which means, when and how many times, and what their responses were, to ensure smooth communication and avoid sending too many requests in a short time period. Also, be aware of information overload (e.g. when briefing stakeholders): there is a limit of how much information people are able and willing to digest.

Applying the ITF for contacting, inviting and engaging stakeholders

The INTERLACE project works with an Impact Task Force (ITF), a living pool of stakeholders to review products as end-users. Members of the ITF consist of end-users, experts of the consortium and representatives of the CNA's, the Advisory board and sister projects. As end-users, they define and help set priorities for product requirements, do regular reviews or testing, and provide feedback. The ITF validates the end products and arguments why certain products might change.

Stakeholders are invited to subscribe to the ITF, by indicating their interest and availability, and providing more details on their profile. This information is stored in the ITF database and managed by an ITF-manager. It is also the ITF-manager who matches ITF-stakeholders to the relevant products, upon request of the product lead. This results in ITF subgroups per product. The matching process is based on a set of criteria:

- End user profile: experience, expertise, sector of activity, etc.;
- Interest of ITF member in the product;
- Inclusivity: geographical representation (EU-CELAC), gender, etc.;
- Workload: product development schedule versus availability of stakeholder.

It is the ITF-manager who initiates the first contact with stakeholders, to avoid multiple requests by different product leads. Once participation to an ITF subgroup is confirmed, it is the product lead who organizes the engagement activities with the ITF-subgroup.

Good practices for communication

Not just with the first contact, but through all communication with stakeholders tailored communication should be applied. Besides tailoring your communication to the stakeholders' role and group, the following considerations help as well to make your messages more meaningful and effective:

- Socio-cultural considerations: do I need to adapt my language for the stakeholder? E.g., applying more formal language when communicating with a decision maker such as a mayor.
- Knowledge level: do I need to simplify my language for the stakeholder? E.g. when communicating with scientists or experts, technical terms can be used, with other stakeholders they should rather be avoided.
- Relevance: can I link the communication about my engagement activities to a bigger picture/story relevant to the stakeholder? E.g., certain INTERLACE products might be linked to other ongoing processes in the city.
- What frequency for communication is appreciated?
- Which channels are appreciated for communication?
- Are there any language barriers, due to the nature of the project?

Furthermore, communication with the stakeholder should always be clear and transparent, especially about what is within the scope of engagement and what is not. Often tensions can occur between the expectations of stakeholders (e.g. wanting concrete actions) and the actual aim of engagement. Developers should be careful with making commitments or promises to stakeholders with the risk that they cannot be delivered on.

For more information on communication within INTERLACE we refer to the Communication Strategy.

ACTION 6: Contact individual stakeholders and use clear, tailored communication.

Brief stakeholders thoroughly and timely (well before the engagement activity) to allow for proper preparation.

Step 7. Roles - Transparent and clear engagement

During the engagement activity, the developer should be transparent and clear about the role that the stakeholder has. The bullet list of step 6 already contains important elements to make the setting clear for the stakeholder. Furthermore, it should be clear to the stakeholder who has the decision power, what is done with their input and how binding their input is. Is it the developer who decides what and what not to do with the input from the stakeholders, or is there e.g. a prioritization made together with the stakeholders on what is included and what not? For the shaper's role, the way decisions are made is linked to the call to action that has been selected (see table 7). For end-users this step is less relevant (as the product is already finalized).

The stakeholder must understand the rules of engagement and also the limitations. It is important that you identify with stakeholders which elements cannot be changed to avoid stakeholders thinking they have been misled or their views have not been incorporated (Bradley, 2013).

Chapter 4 presents, among others, a couple of good practices for facilitation.

ACTION 7: Create clarity on the stakeholders' role and what is done with their input during the engagement activity.

Step 8. Follow-up

After each engagement activity, keep the participants informed on the progress of the product or project. This communication should include what happened during the engagement activity and what the engagement outcomes are. For example, if the engagement was about collecting input or feedback, report on how this input or feedback is incorporated in your product development and what the next steps are. Keeping (transparent) contact with the stakeholders increases participation in following activities.

Follow-up communication can happen through different means, e.g., a document with minutes, a report, a separate info-session, an email, a phone-call, a project website, a newsletter, etc.

Follow up on issues raised during consultation as well as clarification of next steps. Communicate what happens after the engagement activities, and how they can stay involved.

ACTION 8: Follow-up with stakeholders after each engagement activity. Report on the outcomes and next steps.

3.3 Review

We apply a learning-by-doing approach for stakeholder engagement. Evaluation is an indispensable step to make sure you are on the right track and to incorporate a feedback-loop and regular reflection on your stakeholder engagement. To evaluate your tailored engagement approach we recommend to collect feedback from the engaged stakeholders and self-reflect after each engagement activity in order to assess whether you need to adjust your approach for future engagement activities.

There are multiple learning purposes on which you can base your review (based on Guijt 2008):

- **Improving operations:** adjusting project outputs and activities to achieve more (e.g., by asking for stakeholder feedback after each activity, or asking user feedback on a product, you can improve your current way of working);
- **Re-adjusting strategy:** questioning assumptions and theories of change (e.g., tracking effects of activities to test effectiveness for influencing change of behaviour). When collecting qualitative feedback from participants after an engagement activity, include questions to assess change after participation;
- **Deepening understanding:** has knowledge increased after trying out something innovative or experimental (e.g. what have project partners and stakeholders learned from implementing an agile workflow);
- **Building trust:** did your communication contribute to increased transparency and participation (e.g., sharing intermediary results among project partners in an open and transparent way, can build a coalition);
- **Sensitising for action:** building a critical mass of support (by sharing results and involving stakeholders, they can act as enablers to take action for change - by using or disseminating the products, taking part in activities, etc).

Adjustments (e.g. do you need additional engagement activities, do you need to invite additional stakeholders, do you need to adjust your format) can be taken up in your implementation plan (step 4). Furthermore, the feedback can be used to adjust your communication, facilitation and other applied practices.

A review moment should be foreseen after each engagement activity and make these moments an integrated part of your iterative engagement process.

Step 9. Feedback

Your stakeholders are a valuable source to collect feedback on the engagement activities. After each engagement activity you can check with the participants how they appreciate(d) the engagement process as well as the communication about it.

Depending on the 'size' of the engagement activity, different ways of collecting feedback can be applied. In case of a one-on-one meeting with an enabler, a (few) informal question(s) can be asked about their thoughts on your engagement approach. In case of larger engagement events, different methods can be applied onsite or afterwards (table 13). Generally, it is recommended to create an evaluation form specific to your engagement activity to collect feedback after the event (see Annex 6 for a template). Questions can be adapted to your definition of success, engagement objective (step 1) and your learning purpose (section 3.3) for a targeted and effective review process.

Some examples of questions that can be asked:

- How did the participants experience the activity overall?
 - What were strengths?
 - What could be improved?
- Did the engagement strategy contribute to your definition of success?
 - For example, if your definition of success is that participants develop new insights, skills or knowledge, include questions to assess their understanding before and after the event.
- Were other relevant stakeholders missing in the event? If yes, which?
 - Suggestions for new stakeholders can be included into a stakeholder database. In case there are follow-up events, these stakeholders can be invited as well.
- Are participants willing to participate in future engagement activities?
- In case you don't have this data (e.g., from a registration- or guest list), include questions about gender, part of which community, etc. to get a good sense of representation and whether this matches with your ambitions.

Additionally, you can collect data through a simple set of indicators to monitor your engagement effort. Indicators can include the number of individuals and stakeholder groups you engaged per engagement activity, the number of engagement activities per product (development), or number of stakeholders that provided feedback. The Guidance on gender, cultural and ethics-related considerations presents a couple of indicators on representativeness, transparency and inclusiveness.

If you collect feedback from stakeholders, ensure that you do something with this feedback and inform them about it.

Table 13. Methods to gather qualitative feedback from participants (Impact Monitoring Guidance).

Type of feedback	Description of methods
Onsite feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participants fill out an evaluation form at the end of the event (analogue or digital); ● Participants leave their feedback using a post-it on a pinboard. Optionally, the organisers could take a photo of the nicest feedback post-it on the board and make a Twitter/Instagram post. Partners and others re-post it; ● Participants are interviewed and provide quotes; ● Small group discussions with selected guests during the breaks; ● Playful ways to collect feedback on specific questions (only for in person meetings): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ask a question and have a bucket for each of the possible answers. Give each of the guests a ball (or something similar) to put in the bucket that is showing the statement they agree with; ○ Participants leave their badge in either the Yes or No box. The question above both boxes could be: Have you learned something new today that will change your work ahead? Will you attend other conferences about the subject of this event? Have you met guests with whom you aim to stay in touch or co-operate in the future? Do you feel somebody has benefited from your idea today? ● Playful ways to collect feedback on the overall event: Pin three emoticons on the wall (a sad/indifferent/happy face) and ask guests to put stickers on one of the faces to express their appreciation of the event; ● Poll.
Feedback after the event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Feedback survey filled in by event participants (analogue or digital format such as Google Forms), see e.g. the template in Annex 6; ● Observation: notes and photos from the event; ● Telephone interviews with selected guests (E.g., key stakeholders from different categories).
Content Analysis	<p>Find out what people are saying on social media channels, review websites and blogs. Set up Google Alerts and run specific Google searches to find the content online: Has any of the project / issue / project finding been mentioned? Positively or negatively? Has any of the speakers/participants been quoted? Have they initiated any conversation online?</p>

ACTION 9: Develop a tailored list of questions, based on your engagement objective and learning purpose, decide on the appropriate method and collect feedback.

Step 10. Reflect & Improve

You can reflect on the engagement activity with the results from your stakeholder feedback, indicators and your own observations. Durham et al. (2014) consider three areas which can be reflected upon:

- The success of the engagement:
 - Was the purpose and scope of my engagement activity clear?
 - Have the aims and the objectives of the engagement activity been met?
 - Did the stakeholders have realistic expectations about the scope (what is and what is not possible)?
- The process of engagement:
 - What worked well and less well (during planning, engaging and reviewing)? Why?
 - Were the selected format(s), methods and tools appropriate?
 - Was the stakeholder representation good? Why (not)?
 - How was the communication with stakeholders before, during and after the activity?
 - Was the timing realistic for the preparation and execution of the activity?
 - Were the costs reasonable / was there sufficient budget?
- The impact of the engagement:
 - Did the engagement activity have desired outcomes? Why (not)?
 - Did the engagement activity deliver on the promises made to stakeholders?

A list of actions to improve your engagement approach can be made based on the reflection. For example, the review might indicate that women were underrepresented during your engagement activity. Actions can be identified such as sending targeted invitations to women (organisations). Or from your stakeholder feedback you learned that there was too little time to properly participate during the event. This feedback can be used to plan and organize your next event more timely.

ACTION 10: Reflect on your engagement activity based on feedback from your stakeholders and your own observations and distil actions for improvement.

4. Good practices

Engagement activities will always be tailored to the local context and aspired goals. Nevertheless, there are a number of good practices to be aware of at all times. Table 14 gives an overview of good practices that can be incorporated into the Engagement Roadmap.

Table 14. Overview of good practices (Wates, 2000; AccountAbility, 2015).

PLAN - PROCESS	
<p>Now is the right time The best time to start involving people is at the beginning of any programme. The earlier the better.</p>	<p>Walk before you run Developing a participatory culture takes time. Start by using simple participation methods and work up to using more complex ones as experience and confidence grow.</p>
<p>Plan your own process carefully Careful planning of the process is vital. Avoid rushing into any one approach. Look at alternatives. Design a process to suit the circumstances. This may well involve combining a range of methods or devising new ones.</p>	<p>Plan for the local context Develop unique strategies for each context. Understand local characteristics and use them as a starting point for planning.</p>
<p>Process as important as product The way that things are done is often as important as the end result. But remember that the aim is implementation. Participation is important, but is not an end in itself.</p>	<p>Prepare properly The most successful activities are invariably those on which sufficient time and effort have been given to preliminary organisation and engaging those who may be interested.</p>
<p>Flexibility Be prepared to modify processes as circumstances dictate. Avoid inflexible methods and strategies.</p>	<p>Mixture of methods Use a variety of methods as different people will want to take part in different ways.</p>
<p>Respect cultural context Make sure that your approach is suitable for the cultural context in which you are working. Consider local attitudes to gender, informal livelihoods, social groupings, speaking out in public and so on.</p>	
ENGAGE - STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT	
<p>Involve all sections of the community People of different ages, gender, backgrounds and cultures almost invariably have different perspectives. Ensure that a full spectrum of the community is involved. This is usually far more important than involving large numbers.</p>	<p>Quality not quantity There is no such thing as a perfect participation process. Any participation is better than none and the quality of participation is more important than the numbers involved.</p>
<p>Respect local knowledge All people, whether literate or not, whether rich or poor, whether children, women or men, have a remarkable understanding of their surroundings and are capable of analysing and assessing their situation. Respect local perceptions, choices and abilities and involve local people in setting goals and strategies.</p>	<p>Visualise People can participate far more effectively if information is presented visually rather than in words. Use graphics, maps, illustrations, cartoons, drawings, photomontages and models wherever possible. Make the process itself visible by using flipcharts, sticky notes, etc.</p>
<p>Trust Start from a position of trusting others and generally this will be reciprocated. Lack of trust is usually due to lack of information.</p>	<p>Have fun This is a great opportunity to meet people and have fun. The most interesting and sustainable environments have been produced where people have enjoyed creating them.</p>

ENGAGE - STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT	
<p>Record and document Make sure participation activities are properly recorded and documented to see who has been involved and how. Such records can be invaluable at a later stage.</p>	<p>Follow up Lack of follow-up is the most common failing. Make sure you set aside time and resources for documenting, publicising and acting on the results.</p>
ENGAGE - FACILITATION	
<p>Stay neutral Avoid assigning intentions, beliefs or motives to others. Ask others questions instead of stating untested assumptions about them.</p>	<p>Right to not engage Honour each party's right to "pass" if he or she is not ready or willing to speak</p>
<p>Listen Allow others to express their opinions completely.</p>	<p>Equal opportunity for all Make sure that the opportunities for input are evenly distributed.</p>
<p>Respect confidentiality Respect all confidentiality or anonymity requests that the group has agreed to honour.</p>	<p>Use time wisely Be mindful of people's time investment: use group time to engage and exchange, not to prepare individually.</p>
ENGAGE - COMMUNICATION	
<p>Communicate Use all available media to let people know what you are doing and how they can get involved.</p>	<p>Be transparent The objectives and people's roles should be clear and transparent at events.</p>
<p>Be honest Be open and straightforward about the nature of any activity. People will generally participate more enthusiastically if they know something can be achieved through their participation. If there is only a small chance of positive change as a result of people participating, say so.</p>	<p>Avoid jargon Use plain language; avoid complexity. Jargon prevents people from engaging and is usually a smokescreen to hide incompetence, ignorance or arrogance. Local stakeholders (with experience with the local context and/or participatory processes) can help you 'language proof' your messages beforehand.</p>
REVIEW	
<p>Reflect on achieving objectives Regularly monitor progress to ensure that initiatives are built on and objectives achieved. Periodic review sessions can be very valuable to maintain momentum and involvement.</p>	

5. Troubleshooting

Besides being aware of good practices, potential risks and challenges during stakeholder engagement should also be taken into account. Due to the unpredictable nature of engagement activities, certain risks may occur, such as failing to deliver on promised outcomes, unrealistic expectations, loss of trust or reputation (Gray, 2008).

There are some specific risks and challenges for stakeholder engagement, related to the INTERLACE project, presented in table 15. For each risk or challenge, potential solutions or recommendations are proposed.

Table 15. Risks and challenges during engagement processes of the INTERLACE project.

Risks / challenges	Potential solutions / recommendations
<p>Different locations and time zones allow for less 'live' interaction and meeting opportunities.</p> <p><i>This refers to interactions within the consortium, the Impact Task Force or global online events. It applies less to local stakeholder activities in cities.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When planning stakeholder engagement activities, take into account feasible time schedules for all. A doodle could be shared to find a suitable time for all. • Use the Product Lab to interact with stakeholders: they can read updates or provide feedback at a time of their choice.
<p>Language barriers: there is no single project language, but multiple project languages (English, Spanish, German, Polish, Catalan). It is a challenge to provide all information, documents etc. in multiple languages when interacting with local stakeholders. Simultaneous translations during meetings and translation of all project documents, tools and instruments is not always feasible or directly available.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest the extra time in translating relevant documents or presentations in the local language when interacting with stakeholders. Use online translation tools such as DeepL or Google Translate, or ask your local knowledge broker or other consortium partners for support. • Adhere to good practices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ "Avoid jargon" ○ "Visualise"
<p>Different cultures: different contexts, understandings, realities and expectations among stakeholders in different countries adds an extra dimension to stakeholder engagement.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be mindful about cultural differences and take this as an opportunity to learn and exchange knowledge. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adhere to good practices: ○ "Respect cultural context" ○ "Respect local knowledge" ○ "Plan for the local context" • Consult the Guidance on gender, cultural and ethics-related considerations for additional information on cultural differences and how to address them.

Risks / challenges	Potential solutions / recommendations
<p>Covid-19: due to the global pandemic, live meetings or activities with project partners and wider stakeholders are more complicated to organize, or have to be postponed. Besides these practical consequences, there are also effects on human interaction, getting to know each other, gaining trust, etc. Covid-19 has challenged the effective engagement of stakeholders, both live and virtual.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging with stakeholders in an online environment is different, but totally feasible when using good online tools such as Miro, Mural, Mentimeter, Slido, etc. • Assess if your audience has access or is familiar with the online tools mentioned above. You might need to consider more common and accessible applications such as Whatsapp or FaceBook. • More examples of online collaboration tools and virtual icebreakers: Collaboration Superpowers • Consider to hold engagement activities in smaller groups outdoors, to decrease infection risks. E.g. one-on-one walking interviews / interactions with stakeholders in their neighbourhood.
<p>Unrealistic expectations: as stakeholders are engaged at a very early stage during product development (agile workflow), a large number of different user requirements/expectations might be expressed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It remains the responsibility of the project deliverable lead to decide on what is feasible within the scope of the project and what not. Ideally, these decisions (including setting priorities), are made with the stakeholders themselves. • Consider using techniques to prioritize user requirements. E.g., the MoSCoW method uses 4 priority groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MUST have (mandatory) ○ SHOULD have (high priority) ○ COULD have (preferred but not necessary) ○ WON'T (can be postponed)
<p>Conflict: risk of conflict between research benefits and potential harm that may arise for stakeholders as well as the risks of ethnic conflicts.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Guidance on gender, cultural, and ethics-related considerations elaborates on risks of conflict and provides practical guidance to be aware of and address this risk.

Risks / challenges	Potential solutions / recommendations
<p>Unbalanced participation due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biased representation of stakeholders; • Key stakeholders missing; • Low turnout; • Low engagement levels; • Power imbalances (dominance by particular individuals). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply a stakeholder analysis (see e.g. Methodology Living Stakeholder Database) to identify new stakeholders that have been missing. • Make your engagement activity as relevant as possible for stakeholders. E.g., by focussing on specific sites and invite stakeholders that are connected to it. • Work with enablers to reach out to stakeholders. They might be able to convince a stakeholder to participate. • Adhere to good practices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “Involve all sections of the community”; ○ “Quality not quantity”. • Consult the Cookbook Virtual Exchange Formats. It is a collection of virtual interactive exchange methods and tools on how to facilitate city-to-city exchange in more innovative, inclusive ways. • Use engagement techniques that focus on inclusion. For example, liberating structures replace or complement conventional practices, to truly include everyone. These microstructures are simple and easy to learn to enable lively participation in groups of any size.
<p>Stakeholder fatigue: multiple stakeholder engagement activities might take place during the project, which might overburden some stakeholders who get multiple requests.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure there are tangible benefits for stakeholders from engaging with your project activity / output / product. • Organize shorter and more efficient meetings. • Keep a list of your own engagement activities and how often you have contacted and engaged with a stakeholder. Avoid too many or multiple requests. Give stakeholders sufficient time between communication, engagement and input/review moments.

Risks / challenges	Potential solutions / recommendations
<p>Tokenism are actions that are the result of pretending to give advantage to those groups in society who are often treated unfairly, in order to give the appearance of fairness (Cambridge Dictionary, 2021).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-tokenistic involvement should be anchored in the respect for participants and their ability to make contributions. This attitude promotes ways to avoid tokenistic user involvement and stimulate active engagement (Romsland et al, 2019). • Non-tokenism requires a 'collaborative arena', which refers to an area that is conducive to creating positive relationships, participation, and the possibility for collaborators to express their opinions and critiques (Romsland et al, 2019). • Take the organisational and practical aspects of the involvement seriously and emphasise the design of the 'collaborative arena' (e.g. create an informal and positive atmosphere via hospitality and sharing a meal) (Romsland et al, 2019). • Not only focus if stakeholders have contributed to the project, but also reflect whether the process has been empowering and participatory or not (Romsland et al, 2019).

While the Engagement Roadmap has been designed to minimize the chances of risks or issues, we recommend being watchful for these potential risks and challenges during the engagement process, and try to identify and address the root cause of any issue or challenge that may arise. However, issues or conflict may be beyond your scope to solve, in that case we recommend looking for alternative formats (e.g. having separate workshops) to still be able to collect input from your stakeholders.

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Find here all publicly available INTERLACE resources: <https://www.interlace-project.eu/node/156>

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Annex 1. Glossary

Activities	An organized event for end-users for knowledge exchange, outreach, networking, etc. through live meetings, webinars, workshops, etc.
Agile	INTERLACE is implementing an agile workflow. This refers to an iterative way of working in short cycles, which allows for early feedback to rapidly learn and improve and deliver more value faster, in complex, unpredictable environments. The goal is to produce highly relevant products with high value. Read more in the INTERLACE Agile Guidance document.
Call to action	An expression of the role a stakeholder is aimed to have within an engagement activity.
Cities Talk Nature	The regional and global CNA's (more details under CNA).
CNA	To facilitate and stimulate city and wider stakeholder exchange and learning, the project uses an exchange mechanism - City Network Accelerators (CNAs) with a multi-level approach: (1) local CNAs: connect INTERLACE cities with their stakeholders; (2) regional CNAs: connect cities and their surrounding areas with other municipalities within the CELAC and EU regions; (3) global CNA: foster an international city knowledge exchange.
Developers	Stakeholders being part of the development team, developing project products and activities (usually project partners).
Enablers	Stakeholders capable of helping the project to reach and engage a diversity of other audiences, or to achieve other desirable impacts (e.g. promoting and disseminating project outputs).
End-users	Stakeholders who use the outputs of the INTERLACE project (products) for real-world applications outside the project.
Engagement activity	Each occasion that engages stakeholders. Each engagement activity has its own objective and subsequently different involved stakeholders and format.
Engagement Roadmap	A logical step to step approach to guide the developer in creating and conducting a tailor-made engagement strategy for their product. See chapter 3.
Hub	The INTERLACE Hub functions as the 'shop window' of the project. It is where the products of the agile workflow process are packaged, promoted and made available to users and the wider NbS community.
Impact Task Force (ITF)	Joint group of all users engaged in product development during the INTERLACE project. Sub-groups of the Impact Task Force will use and test specific products.
Interested public	Interested stakeholders capable of generating 'bottom-up' support for NbS, and help translate the work of INTERLACE to other stakeholders (improved understanding, increased relevance).
Logbook	The INTERLACE Logbook aims to facilitate the collection and exchange of information that is relevant on project level. The Google sheet contains key information on each city and helps to keep track of reporting needs.
NbS	Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are defined by IUCN as "actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits".
Participation	Stakeholders taking part or becoming involved in INTERLACE product development or events.

Platforms	INTERLACE is using a series of platforms in the project to interact with stakeholders. Please refer to table 3 for an overview.
Platform managers	Responsible for overseeing the development and management of the platform.
Products	In INTERLACE, 'products' are all the things that will be produced for cities and other targeted stakeholder groups: reports, guidelines, policy instruments, databases, online tools, activities, events, communication products, the project web-platform and more.
Product Lab	Online platform where the tools and resources created by the project will be made available for testing and feedback (integrated in the Hub).
Product vision	A product vision describes what a product should look like. It clearly states what problems the product aims to resolve or what ambitions it aims to achieve. A clear product vision helps to inspire and motivate people.
Shapers	Stakeholders who provide input and feedback on project outputs.
Stakeholders	Any group or individual who is potentially, directly or indirectly, interested in, affected by, or have an influence or impact on the project, its outputs or activities. This can include stakeholders that are close to the project and provide it with essential resources (knowledge, expertise, etc.) or stakeholders that are impacted by or have influence over the city challenges or interventions planned to address the challenges.
Stakeholder engagement	A broad, inclusive and continuous process and an open, constructive relationship between a project and those potentially affected by or interested in it for a purpose to achieve accepted outcomes.
Stakeholder groups	Stakeholders are grouped based on their profession, knowledge, expertise or background, and are also grouped based on matching needs or interests.
Stakeholder mapping	A logical categorization of stakeholders which require adapted approaches to engagement within INTERLACE.
Stakeholder roles	Stakeholders are grouped based on their role or function within the INTERLACE project.
Sustainable engagement	Engaging stakeholders long-term and in a meaningful way or in other words, sustaining relationships and commitments between INTERLACE partners and its stakeholders.
User stories	Needs and ideas related to a product, expressed by the user of that product ('user requirements'). A user story is about the user: who the user is, what they want from the product, and why.

Annex 2. Example Engagement Roadmap

Table 16 presents each step of the Engagement Roadmap with a fictional example of how the actions could be applied. The example showcases how the SES can be conducted for the organization of engagement activities for the NbS gaming activity that will be organized in each INTERLACE city.

Table 16. Overview of actions with an fictional example of how it could be applied to the NbS gaming event.

Step	Action	Example – NbS gaming event using Minecraft (WP5)
	Plan	
0	Before setting up an engagement strategy, the development team starts the agile workflow and defines and validates the product vision.	<p>The development team (OPPLA and WWF) draft a preliminary product vision and organize an (online) workshop with each city and representatives of youth to discuss and validate the product vision and to collect user stories (what form will the event take, for who, and why - what does the city want to get out of the event). There are two user-groups: 1) the INTERLACE cities that will apply the Minecraft game to collect ideas and input from young people who are invited to design restorative NbS for their neighbourhoods and 2) children and youth who will use Minecraft to design their ideas.</p> <p>The result of this workshop is a validated product vision by all parties:</p> <p>“For the INTERLACE cities, who want to involve youth into the design and planning of NbS, the Minecraft game will be adapted to the local intervention sites to engage and encourage youth to participate in a creative designing process for local restorative NbS. Unlike regular participatory processes, youth will be engaged in a creative world that they are familiar with.”</p>
1	Define your engagement objectives for your product / activity development in terms of ‘calls to action’ and added value. Specify which role is needed during what phase of your product / activity development.	<p>The development team identified the following engagement objectives for the development of the product:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shapers are needed to give advice on the intervention site where the Minecraft game will be applied in order to tailor the game environment to the local context; 2. Enablers are needed to provide access to local schools in order to inform and invite them to participate in the project; 3. Enablers are needed to disseminate/promote the activity to the youth in order to inform and let them participate in the activity; 4. Shapers are needed to review the tailored game environment in order to adjust details and validate it; 5. End-users will participate in the Minecraft gaming event in order for the cities to collect creative design ideas for NbS at the local intervention site.
2	<p>Identify stakeholders:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define which stakeholder group(s) you want to engage for each engagement objective, taking into account diversity and inclusiveness. 2. Define specific stakeholders you want to engage. Write down the organizations and when applicable the departments and individuals. 3. Reflect whether you can reach all the stakeholders you aim to engage, and 	<p>The following stakeholder groups are identified:</p> <p>Governmental authorities, specifically the local environment department, planning department and education department</p> <p>Added value for INTERLACE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal support within municipal departments for INTERLACE products; • INTERLACE products contributing to urban (NbS) planning. <p>Benefit for governmental authorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative alternatives / inspiration for NbS; • Learning and sharing knowledge with children and youth. <p>Benefit for role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shaper: steer content of the Minecraft game environment to meet the context of the local intervention site and by doing so increase usefulness and relevance; • Enabler: being able to give a voice to an underrepresented group, in this case youth. <p>Civil Society, specifically youth</p> <p>Added value for INTERLACE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity to issues/needs/wishes of youth;

	<p>whether enablers need to be identified.</p> <p>4. Identify benefits for the stakeholders related to their engagement, based on their role and the group they are part of. Additionally, sectoral motivations can be taken into account as well as synergies that go beyond the INTERLACE project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raising awareness and participation. <p>Benefit for civil society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in INTERLACE activities which may influence urban design decisions; Possibilities to address their agenda in INTERLACE cities and have influence on the causes they stand for; Increased sense of ownership. <p>Benefit for role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> End-user: Local knowledge based planning of NbS. <p>Education sector, specifically local schools</p> <p>Added value for INTERLACE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have access / get input from a younger generation; Share knowledge to students / youth on the importance of urban green. <p>Benefit for education sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to new knowledge and insights from INTERLACE scientific research; Opportunity for youth / students to provide input on their cities green spaces; Opportunities to link to environmental education projects (or to set up such projects). <p>Benefit for role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shaper: steer content of the Minecraft game environment to meet the context of the intervention site and by doing so increase usefulness and relevance; Enabler: being able to give an underrepresented group a voice.
3	<p>Select an appropriate format for each engagement objective.</p>	<p>The following formats were selected for each engagement objective:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> An online Zoom meeting with each city to learn about the local intervention sites; An online meeting with enablers of each city to give them guidance on selecting and inviting local and suitable schools; An online meeting with enablers of each school to engage them on informing and recruiting youth; An online meeting with shapers to collect feedback on the locally adapted Minecraft world; Multiple physical events are organized at the local school close to the intervention site to give the participating students sufficient time to design NbS in Minecraft.
4	<p>Create a (living) implementation plan which presents a logical order of your engagement activities as well as the what, when, why, who and how?</p>	<p>The following implementation plan is made:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Shapers are needed to provide advice on the intervention site to which the Minecraft game will be applied in order to tailor the games environment to the local context <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Who: local environment department, planning department and education department; Benefit: steer content of products to meet the context of the INTERLACE cities and by doing so increase usefulness and relevance; How: online meeting; When: 12-01-2021. Enablers are needed to provide access to local schools in order to inform and invite them to participate in the project <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Who: education department; Benefit: being able to give an underrepresented group a voice; How: online meeting; When: 19-01-2021. Enablers are needed to disseminate/promote the activity to the youth in order to inform and let them participate in the activity <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Who: local schools;

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Benefit: being able to give their students a voice as well as access to new knowledge and insights from INTERLACE; c. How: online meeting; d. When: 15-03-2021. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Shapers are needed to review the tailored game environment in order to adjust details and validate it <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Who: local environment department, planning department, education department and local schools; b. Benefit: steer content of products to meet the context of the INTERLACE cities and by doing so increase usefulness and relevance; c. How: online meeting; d. When: 30-03-2021. 5. End-users will participate in the Minecraft gaming event in order for cities to collect creative design ideas for NbS at the local intervention site <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Who: youth; b. Benefit: influence the design of a local NbS so that it better reflects the interests and wishes of young people; c. How: 3 physical meetings; d. When: 28-04-2021 to 30-04-2021.
	Engage	Phase 2 and 3 focus on single engagement activities. In these phases the 5th engagement activity (End-users will participate in the Minecraft gaming event) is further elaborated.
5	<p>Make a detailed script to support the organization of your engagement activity.</p> <p>Share the plans of your engagement activity with the stakeholders and collect feedback to increase relevance and impact of your activity.</p>	<p>The development team prepares a detailed script (see Annex 5) to prepare for the event. The script contains the preparation (what equipment is needed, who is responsible for what and other logistics), the program for the day itself (timing, explanation of each step, who is responsible) and what actions are needed after the event (collecting feedback, writing report, etc.).</p> <p>The development team shares their initial plans (agenda, logistics, etc.) for the Minecraft gaming event with the municipal departments, local schools and possibly a couple of participating students to align expectations and to fine tune the plans.</p>
6	<p>Contact individual stakeholders and use clear, tailored communication.</p> <p>Brief stakeholders thoroughly and timely (well before the engagement activity to allow for proper preparation).</p>	<p>The invitation contains the following elements:</p> <p>Product vision: “For the INTERLACE cities, who want to involve youth into the planning of NbS, the Minecraft game will be adapted to the local intervention sites to engage and encourage youth to participate in a creative designing process for local NbS. Unlike regular participatory processes, youth will be engaged in a creative world that they are familiar with”</p> <p>The call to action + added value: “Local youth are invited to participate in the Minecraft gaming event in order for cities to collect creative design ideas for NbS at the local intervention site”</p> <p>What is expected of them: To be available for 3 afternoons at the local school and to think about greening a local vacant terrain in a virtual world. The event is for free. PC’s with Minecraft are accessible at the school.</p> <p>Benefits for them (role + group): When participating you are able to use your ideas to influence the design of a local vacant terrain so that it better reflects the wishes of young people and will be used by them in the future.</p> <p>Format + timeline: The event will happen at your local school from 28th till the 30th of April. After a short introduction, computers will be available in the classroom. On the final day, the different worlds will be shared among the students and the top 5 favorite worlds will be presented to the municipality.</p> <p>Logistical and practical information about the engagement: Location of the school + classroom number. On the first day be present 15 minutes before the event starts and notify your presence at the welcome desk.</p> <p>How to respond to the invitation: Please respond to this email if you wish to register for the event. Registration is possible until the 14th of April 2021.</p>

7	Create clarity on the stakeholders' role and what is done with their input during the engagement activity.	The development team communicates clearly in the invitation as well as during the event that the top 5 favorite worlds/designs in Minecraft will be presented to the municipality. Following a presentation of each Minecraft design, the students can vote which worlds/designs they like most. The municipality can select elements of the Minecraft designs and incorporate it in the final design of the vacant terrain.
8	Follow-up with stakeholders after each engagement activity. Report on the outcomes and next steps.	The development team creates a video showcasing the 5 favorite NbS designs of the students and shares it with the school and posts it on (local) social media. The municipality will communicate which elements they have used in the final design of the intervention site. Solutions will be shared between cities via the Hub, with opportunities for participants to learn from each other.
Review		
9	Feedback from stakeholders: Develop a tailored list of questions, based on your engagement objective and learning purpose, decide on the appropriate method and collect feedback.	<p>The development team prepares an online survey that will be shared with the participants. The survey will assess how they experienced the activity, what they learned from the activity, what were its strengths and what could be improved. Furthermore, the participants will be asked to score how satisfied they were with the activity (from 1 to 10) (see step 3.2).</p> <p>The development team collects data on the number of students participating, number of feedback collected and the satisfaction of the activity. Data on inclusivity will be also collected (see Guidance on gender, cultural and ethics-related considerations).</p>
10	Reflection: Reflect on your engagement activity based on feedback from your stakeholders and your own observations and distil actions for improvement.	Based on the feedback collected and an internal reflection, the development team identifies a number of actions to improve the Minecraft gaming event for the other INTERLACE cities.

Annex 3. Building the strategy

For the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SES) the INTERLACE **Agile workflow** was applied, which means that users are involved throughout the process to regularly provide feedback on early versions and, to a certain degree, participate in the making of the product.

At the start of the development of the SES, an online user-workshop was organized with the aid of a Miro board (Annex 4). The **targeted users** were the platform managers of the local City Network Accelerators (CNA), of the Impact Task Force (ITF), of the INTERLACE Hub and outreach activities.

These project partners who will make use of the SES, discussed the **product vision** and shared **user stories** (see table 17). User stories describe who the user is (role in the project), what the user wants (SES requirements, functionality) and why the user needs this product (benefits).

Table 17. Product vision and user stories for the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

	<p>Product vision <i>What is the purpose for creating this product? Which positive change should it bring about?</i></p> <p><i>“A roadmap with clear and easy to use pathways to facilitate stakeholder engagement will be prepared, to inspire and trigger innovative and sustainable engagement for INTERLACE partners who engage with stakeholders to maximise impact and efficiency”.</i></p> <p>The users visualized the product vision of the stakeholder engagement strategy as an image of a swan. The swan symbolizes a clear and smooth experience for users (the visible part of the swan swimming), without knowing the complexity of the process underneath the surface.</p>
<p>Summary of user stories</p>	
<p>Stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder mapping needed: how to structure and segment different audiences (groups with similar needs and approach); • clarify and prioritise which stakeholders to focus on; • engage beyond the usual suspects, to get new perspectives; • representative group of stakeholders for input/feedback; • establish a constructive relationship between ITF members and task leads; • involve the advisory board.

<p>Content – Questions to be answered by the SES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How to generate, facilitate and maintain long term, sustainable interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ find a win-win for all parties involved (starting point!); ○ define trigger points - how to spark interest; ○ how to avoid fatigue and burn out; ○ how to make stakeholders feel to be part of INTERLACE. ● How to organize knowledge exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Learn from each other at different stages; ○ Share advices built on past experiences; ○ Facilitate learning from each other between CFPs, improve the process. ● Engagement process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ understand the life-cycle of stakeholder engagement and actions to be taken at different stages; ○ understand 'upstream and downstream' processes - i.e. where have stakeholders already been in terms of their engagement with INTERLACE and where do we need to help them go next?; ○ make stakeholders interactions with the project as easy and enjoyable as possible; ○ set out a smooth and clear, easy to use journey for all who is involved; ○ guidance to capture how the engagement process is working in diverse contexts; ○ understand different barriers and difficulties and how to address them; ○ how to deal with covid-19.
<p>Format</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Needs to be easy to use (clear headlines, clear questions being answered, diagrams, summary infographics, 1-2 pager quick guide,...); ● Clear pathway/journey/ life-cycle of stakeholder engagement (different steps/actions at each stage and clear end result); ● Something original / different (e.g. webpage with live links); ● Use clear examples.
<p>Links - Understand how it all fits together</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agile workflow: Make sure the products are co-produced by a representative group of users; ● Guidance on gender, cultural, and ethics-related considerations: to foster participation of diverse stakeholders. How to operationalize it, how to identify and address problems; ● Impact Task Force: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ link profile questionnaire or entry point on Hub; ○ impact, applicability, replicability of the products generated within INTERLACE. ● Communication plan: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ which messages should we be using when communicating with each stakeholder group; ○ communicate to stakeholders how their inputs are being used.
<p>Indicators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Impact indicators; ● Evaluation indicators: when do I know I am doing it right? (self-check); ● Barometer (Cities Talk Nature): include at least one indicator on how to measure this engagement; ● Feedback on the process itself (from stakeholders themselves).

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Based on the user stories, a **stakeholder mapping** exercise was conducted which contributed to tailoring the stakeholder engagement strategy to the context of INTERLACE (see chapter 2).

Furthermore, a **literature scan** was conducted to find relevant scientific articles and practical guidelines addressing stakeholder engagement. The literature is used for the underlying theoretical basis as well as practical (good practice) lists or guides used in this stakeholder engagement strategy. Additionally, **meetings with CFP's** (so far only with CBIMA, Granollers and Metropolia Krakowska) were organized to collect input on their stakeholder engagement plans, challenges, needs and good practices. The findings from these meetings were used (besides the literature) to develop the good practices and Engagement Roadmap (chapter 3).

Annex 4: Template Miro board

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

MIRO TEMPLATE AGILE WORKFLOW

PRODUCT VISION

What is your purpose for creating the product?
Which positive change should it bring about?

TEMPLATE for [our targeted users], who [user's need], the [product] is a [product description] that [specific benefits and added value]. Unlike [current methods, existing products, status quo], our product [main differentiators].

QUESTIONS:

Have a look at the proposed product vision:

- Are we considering the right users (internal / external)?
- A document with good practices: any additions?

PROPOSAL PRODUCT VISION

Write down your draft proposal of your product vision and fine-tune / agree / finalize with your users

Goals:

- facilitate sustainable engagement
- set out a smooth and clear, easy to use journey for all who is involved
- provide a win-win for all parties involved
- involve all potential stakeholders
- share advices from past experiences

vision = clear pathway for users

vision = swan

focus on all stakeholders (local/regional/global)	Audience analysis: how to structure and segment different audiences (groups with similar needs)
Decide on which stakeholders to focus on	focus on stakeholders who are involved in product development
stakeholder mapping needed > different categories / audiences (eg different approach engagement policy levels)	starting point: find win-win for all parties involved
Format: webpage? live links etc	clear headlines; clear questions being answered; diagrams, summary infographic
Covid effect on engagement?	involve Advisory board

TARGETED USERS	USER NEEDS		ADDED VALUE
"Platform managers" (internal project users)	1-2 pager quick guide	How to generate interest How to keep the interest alive during a long period	tips, tools, processes, examples
City Focal points			
Knowledge brokers			

USER STORIES

Use a format that identifies: who the user is, what they need, and for what purpose (the why)

TEMPLATE "As a [description of user], I need a [functionality] in order to [benefit]"

EXAMPLES
 Add some (potential) examples for your product to get the conversation started
 "As a [platform manager of a local CNA], I need [guidelines] in order to [effectively engage stakeholders]".
 "As a [knowledge broker], I need [inspiration] in order to [ensure stakeholders continue to be engaged]".
 "As the [ITF manager], I need [advice] in order to [deal with barriers to engagement]"

Fill in your own user story: what do you, as a user of the stakeholder engagement strategy, expect or need.

Annex 5. Template script for workshops

<p>INTERLACE Name workshop</p> <p>--Script--</p>

Organizers:

Objective(s):

-

Expected outcome(s):

-

Location:

(Address, building, room(s))

Support:

Who?	Role?	Check
	(E.g. host)	
	(E.g. moderator)	
	(E.g. facilitator breakout group)	
	(E.g. note taker)	

Preparation:

What?	Who?	By when?	Check
(E.g. arrange location)			
(E.g. arrange food and drinks)			
(E.g. invite participants)			
(E.g. develop tailored methodology)			

Equipment:

What?	Who?	Check
(E.g. beamer)		
(E.g. post-its and pens)		
(E.g. banners)		

Participants:

Who?	Comments	Invited?	Accepted?
	(E.g. arrives 1 hour later)		
	(E.g. vegetarian)		

Invitation email:

See step 6.

WORKSHOP SCRIPT

Start	End	Program	Explanation	Who (lead)?	Who else (support)?	Format	Supplies
9:15	9:30	Walk-in	Participants arrive, can get a coffee and find a seat				Coffee, tea, water and cookies
9:30	9:45	Welcome	Participants are welcomed and the agenda of the day is presented			Presentation	Beamer, laptop/pc, PowerPoint
9:45	10:15	Key-note speech	Presentation on			Presentation	Beamer, laptop/pc, PowerPoint
10:15	11:00	Brainstorm	Brainstorm on ... Participants will be divided into groups of ... The following questions will be asked: ... etc.			Break-out groups	Sheets, post-its, pens, voice-recorders
		Coffee break					Coffee, tea, water and cookies
		Lunch break					Sandwiches, drinks
		Coffee break					Coffee, tea, water and cookies
		Closure	Round up the workshop and thank the participants				

FOLLOW-UP ACTIONS: ASSEMBLING INPUT, ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION

What?	Who?	By when?
(E.g. send out evaluation form)		
(E.g. digitize recordings, notes and/or post-its)		
(E.g. analyse collected input)		
(E.g. write report and send to the participants)		

Annex 6. Template evaluation form

This template has originally been presented in the Impact Monitoring Guidance.

Name of the event: [prefilled by event organiser]; Date & Location: [prefilled by event organiser]

What is your professional background?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy making, city government / administration
<input type="checkbox"/>	City planning, architecture
<input type="checkbox"/>	Business, industry
<input type="checkbox"/>	Investment, financial sector
<input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific community (university / research centre)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Civil society, NGOs
<input type="checkbox"/>	Customers
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media and communications
<input type="checkbox"/>	General public (citizens etc.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other, please describe:

Scale: 1 = poor; 2 = fair; 3 = good; 4 = very good; 5 = excellent

CONTENT AND FORMAT

1. How would you rate the event in terms of content?

1 2 3 4 5

2. What did you find the most interesting?

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3. Have you learned anything new? If so what?

4. What one idea or action will you take away from today's event to apply in your work/practice?

5. Were any topics missing? If so, which? Were you expecting something different than what this event turned out to be? If so, how?

6. How would you evaluate the structure/format of the event?

1 2 3 4 5

7. In case you evaluated the format as 'poor or fair' (1 or 2), please indicate why. In case you particularly liked a specific format, please let us know.

8. On a scale from 1 to 5 (where 1 is 'closed-minded, fixed viewpoints' and 5 is 'open, respectful, consensus-oriented') – in your opinion, to what extent did the moderation promote an open and respectful discussion?

1 2 3 4 5

NETWORKING AND PARTICIPANTS

9. How would you rate the opportunities for networking and exchanging ideas at the event?

1 2 3 4 5

10. What were the most important/interesting new connections that you made today? Do you feel like you will keep in touch with any of the individuals you had a chance to exchange with today?

11. How would you rate the heterogeneity of the workshops participants (in terms of expertise, affiliation, views, background, gender)?

1 2 3 4 5

12. In case you evaluated the group as unbalanced, which group do you consider to be underrepresented (e.g. city government/administration, urban planners, business/industry, universities/research centres, NGOs/CSOs, women, other underrepresented groups)?

EVENT ORGANISATION

13. How would you rate this event's logistical organisation?

1 2 3 4 5

14. What would you have done differently?

15. Other general comments :

INTERLACE is a four year project that will empower and equip European and Latin American cities to restore urban ecosystems, resulting in more liveable, resilient and inclusive cities that benefit people and nature.

interlace-project.eu

INTERLACE es un proyecto de cuatro años que busca empoderar y soportar ciudades de Europa y América Latina en la restauración de ecosistemas urbanos, resultando en ciudades más vivibles, inclusivas y resilientes para el beneficio de la gente y la naturaleza.

Project Partners

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